

LEVERAGING MARKETING ACTIVITIES IN MICRO-ENTERPRISES TO DRIVE WOMEN'S EMPOWERMENT: A STRUCTURAL EQUATION ANALYSIS

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Abstract

This study investigates how women's participation in micro-enterprise marketing activities contributes to their empowerment. Researchers conducted a comprehensive review of literature on women's empowerment, micro-enterprises, social capital, and self-help groups, focusing on how marketing efforts can enhance women's roles in these enterprises. Primary data was collected through a self-administered, pre-tested questionnaire, targeting participants with at least three years of experience in micro-enterprise marketing activities. A multi-stage sampling strategy was employed to gather the necessary data. The conceptual framework for assessing women's empowerment through marketing activities in micro-enterprises includes three core variables. Research inquiries and hypotheses were formulated, and exploratory factor analysis (EFA) and confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) were used to validate the constructs. Structural equation modeling (SEM) was applied to evaluate the relationships among the variables. The results highlight that strengthening social capital through marketing networks increases women's control and independence in decision-making within their businesses. This emphasizes the role of marketing-related social networks in enhancing women's economic empowerment, particularly in the context of India's Kudumbashree program. The study provides valuable theoretical insights into how marketing activities, supported by social capital, can promote financial autonomy and enable women to make more independent social and economic choices.

Keywords: Women Empowerment, Micro-Enterprise, Marketing activities, Social Capital, Economic Autonomy.

INTRODUCTION

India, with a population of 1.31 billion, is the second most populous country globally, accounting for 17% of the world's population, and is projected to surpass China by 2028 (Mathur & Agarwal, 2017). According to the 2011 Census, India had a gender ratio of 943 females per 1000 males, with rural areas showing a higher ratio (949) compared to urban areas (929) (Population Census 2011, n.d.). Despite improvements in the gender ratio

from 933 in 2001 to 943 in 2011, disparities remain, particularly in regions with higher economic activity (Duppatti et al., 2020). These demographic insights are crucial for understanding the socio-economic dynamics affecting women's participation and empowerment in micro-enterprises across rural and urban settings.

Women's empowerment has emerged as a critical focus in the discourse of economic development, particularly in developing economies where gender disparities are prevalent. One of the most effective avenues to drive empowerment is through participation in micro-enterprises, which provide women with opportunities for financial independence, skill development, and leadership roles within their communities. Recent studies emphasize that marketing activities within these micro-enterprises play a significant role in shaping the empowerment trajectory of women. Marketing efforts not only enhance the visibility of the enterprise but also foster skills in communication, negotiation, and financial literacy, which are crucial for decision-making power and autonomy in both social and economic contexts (Samanta, 2021; Kumar & Raj, 2022).

In the context of micro-enterprises, marketing activities serve as a bridge between women and broader social networks, thereby building social capital, which is fundamental to empowerment. Social capital, defined as the value derived from interpersonal networks, trust, and social norms, has been shown to improve women's ability to access resources, make business decisions, and participate in community leadership. Micro-enterprise programs, such as India's Kudumbashree initiative, have demonstrated that marketing activities directly impact the level of social capital women can leverage, ultimately enhancing their roles in decision-making and economic participation (Joseph & Narayanan, 2023). The importance of marketing activities in expanding social networks is further reinforced by their ability to connect women with external markets and stakeholders, providing them with the necessary tools to sustain and grow their businesses.

Given the central role of marketing activities in micro-enterprises, this study seeks to explore how these activities contribute to women's empowerment by leveraging structural equation modeling (SEM). The SEM framework allows for a nuanced examination of the relationships between various factors, such as the extent of women's participation in marketing, the development of social capital, and the subsequent impact on empowerment.

By leveraging social connections, women can access resources, information, and support that are essential for their advancement in various spheres of life (Gupta & Sharma, 2023). This research will contribute to a deeper understanding of how marketing engagement within micro-enterprises acts as a catalyst for building social networks, fostering business growth, and reinforcing women's decision-making capacities. The insights gained will be particularly relevant for policymakers and practitioners interested in using micro-enterprise models to promote long-term economic empowerment and community leadership for women.

Study Objectives

- To analyze the role of marketing activities within micro-enterprises in enhancing women's empowerment.
- To evaluate the relationships between marketing participation, social capital, and empowerment outcomes.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Women's empowerment through participation in micro-enterprises has been increasingly recognized in recent research, with a particular focus on the role of social capital. The literature highlights that social capital significantly enhances women's empowerment by improving their socioeconomic conditions and business outcomes (Agyapong et al., 2017; Kumar et al., 2019). Social capital, in the form of trust, networks, and shared norms, positively influences the performance of micro-enterprises led by women, providing them with a competitive edge and improved financial inclusion (Prakasa, 2018; Devika & Thampi, 2007). In addition to social capital, marketing activities within micro-enterprises play a critical role in empowering women by improving their access to resources and markets, enhancing their visibility, and fostering relationships with external stakeholders, which are crucial for business success (Mahmood et al., 2019). Microfinance institutions, combined with marketing training and social capital development, further contribute to women's empowerment, providing essential tools for business growth and economic independence (Jetti, 2006; Haque et al., 2019).

Research also emphasizes the importance of understanding different dimensions of social capital—cognitive, relational, and structural—in influencing micro-enterprise performance, particularly through marketing practices such as customer outreach and relationship building (Zainol et al., 2017). The integration of trust and reciprocity within social networks helps women entrepreneurs overcome challenges in marketing their products and services, thus improving their decision-making capabilities and market positioning (Putnam, 1993). Additionally, effective marketing practices, supported by social capital, mitigate entrepreneurial risks by creating a safety net through community support, collective action, and improved access to market information (Hoq et al., 2017). This synthesis of studies underscores the vital role that both social capital and marketing strategies play in advancing women's empowerment through their participation in micro-enterprises.

Women's Empowerment and Its Distinct Grounds

Women's empowerment is a multifaceted concept involving control over financial resources, access to knowledge, and belief systems. It leads to the strength to act, collaborate with others, and develop internal power. Empowerment is a process of awareness and conscientization that increases capabilities, enabling greater involvement, leadership, and transformative actions. This includes the ability to influence others and secure necessary resources. Empowerment affects all areas of women's lives, from family and community to broader society, including mental potential for

assertiveness. It provides women the freedom to live as they wish, determine their expertise, and enhance decision-making capacity, significantly contributing to societal economic growth.

A series of studies have highlighted the significant impact of women's participation in micro-enterprise activities on empowerment in India. Programs like Kudumbashree in Kerala and micro-finance through Self Help Groups have promoted women's empowerment. The importance of technical knowledge, skill training, and marketing techniques in enhancing women's economic empowerment through micro-enterprises has been emphasized. Research has underscored the positive impacts of micro-credit programs on women's economic and socio-cultural empowerment, while studies have highlighted overall empowerment across economic, social, and psychological dimensions. These findings indicate that micro-enterprises play a crucial role in fostering women's empowerment in various dimensions.

Micro-Enterprises and Women's Economic Empowerment

Micro-enterprises have been recognized as a powerful tool for promoting women's economic empowerment, particularly in developing countries (Mayoux, 2001). These small-scale businesses, often run from home, provide women with opportunities to generate income, develop entrepreneurial skills, and gain financial independence (Kabeer, 2005). Research has shown that women's participation in micro-enterprises can lead to improved household welfare, increased decision-making power, and enhanced social status (Cheston & Kuhn, 2002). However, the success of these enterprises and their impact on women's empowerment are influenced by various factors, including access to resources, market conditions, and the effectiveness of marketing activities (Kantor, 2003).

Marketing Activities in Micro-Enterprises

Marketing activities play a crucial role in the success of micro-enterprises, particularly those run by women entrepreneurs. Effective marketing can help these businesses identify target customers, develop appropriate products or services, and create sustainable competitive advantages (Blankson et al., 2006). Studies have shown that micro-enterprises engaging in strategic marketing activities tend to perform better in terms of sales, profitability, and growth (O'Dwyer et al., 2009). However, women entrepreneurs in micro-enterprises often face unique challenges in implementing marketing strategies, including limited resources, lack of formal training, and cultural barriers (Jamali, 2009). Despite these challenges, research suggests that even simple marketing activities, such as product differentiation and customer relationship management, can significantly impact the performance of women-led micro-enterprises (Chirwa, 2008).

The Intersection of Marketing and Women's Empowerment

The relationship between marketing activities in micro-enterprises and women's empowerment is complex and multifaceted. While some studies have focused on the direct economic benefits of marketing for women entrepreneurs (Amine & Staub, 2009), others have explored the broader social and psychological impacts. For instance,

engaging in marketing activities can enhance women's self-confidence, decision-making abilities, and social networks (Al-Dajani & Marlow, 2013). Furthermore, successful marketing efforts can lead to increased respect and recognition within the community, challenging traditional gender roles and norms (Kabeer, 2011). However, the extent to which marketing activities contribute to women's empowerment may vary depending on contextual factors such as cultural norms, institutional support, and access to resources (Mair & Marti, 2007).

Structural Equation Modeling in Empowerment Research

Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) has emerged as a valuable tool for analyzing the complex relationships between marketing activities, micro-enterprise performance, and women's empowerment. This statistical technique allows researchers to examine both direct and indirect effects among multiple variables simultaneously, providing a more nuanced understanding of the empowerment process (Hair et al., 2010). Several studies have employed SEM to investigate the pathways through which micro-enterprise activities, including marketing, contribute to various dimensions of women's empowerment (Malhotra & Schuler, 2005). For example, Swain and Wallentin (2009) used SEM to demonstrate how participation in microfinance programs leads to women's empowerment through various intermediary factors. Similarly, SEM can be applied to analyze how specific marketing activities in micro-enterprises influence different aspects of women's empowerment, such as economic independence, decision-making power, and social status (Haugh & Talwar, 2016).

Factors Affecting Women's Empowerment

Research on women's empowerment indicates that households benefit significantly when women play a larger role in decision-making. Empowerment in rural communities is influenced by various factors such as age, education, accessibility to infrastructure, and the type of agricultural production. Older women and those with higher academic qualifications tend to have greater autonomy, with education equity between couples playing a crucial role (Sell & Minot, 2018).

Economic factors are fundamental to women's empowerment. Access to financial resources, including microfinance and savings groups, can significantly enhance women's autonomy and decision-making power (Ganle et al., 2015). Employment and entrepreneurship opportunities allow women to contribute to household income and gain financial independence. Buvinic and O'Donnell (2016) emphasize that women's economic empowerment is crucial for achieving gender equality and sustainable development. Furthermore, property rights and asset ownership are critical economic factors that can empower women by providing them with security and leverage within their families and communities (Meinzen-Dick et al., 2019).

Social and cultural factors greatly influence women's empowerment. Education and literacy are fundamental in expanding women's knowledge, skills, and opportunities (Kabeer, 2005). Social norms, traditions, and religious practices can either hinder or promote women's empowerment, depending on their nature and implementation (Cislaghi

& Heise, 2020). Media representation and awareness campaigns can challenge stereotypes and promote positive role models. Health and reproductive rights, including access to healthcare and family planning services, are also crucial social factors affecting women's empowerment (Prata et al., 2017).

Political and familial factors are interconnected in their impact on women's empowerment. Political participation and representation in decision-making bodies at local and national levels can give women a voice in shaping policies that affect their lives (Domingo et al., 2015). Legal frameworks that ensure gender equality and protect women's rights are essential. Within the family, factors such as decision-making power, division of household labor, and freedom of movement significantly influence women's empowerment (Huis et al., 2017). Support from family members, particularly male relatives, can be instrumental in challenging patriarchal norms and fostering an environment conducive to women's empowerment (Hidrobo et al., 2016).

The Empowerment Nexus: Social Capital, Women's Micro-enterprises, and Marketing Practices

Recent literature highlights a strong nexus between social capital, women's empowerment, and micro-enterprises, particularly through marketing practices. Sanyal (2009) demonstrates how women's participation in microcredit programs enhances their social capital, leading to increased empowerment and collective action. Building on this, Swain and Wallentin (2009) show that women's involvement in microfinance-linked enterprises significantly contributes to their empowerment by expanding their social networks. In the context of marketing practices, Datta and Gailey (2012) illustrate how women-owned micro-enterprises leverage social capital to overcome resource constraints and enhance their market presence. Similarly, Hussain et al. (2018) find that social capital facilitates knowledge sharing and innovation in women-led micro-enterprises, improving their marketing capabilities. Scott et al. (2012) emphasize the role of social media in building social capital for women entrepreneurs, enabling them to extend their market reach. Furthermore, Lindvert et al. (2017) demonstrate how women's social capital, derived from business networks and associations, enhances their access to finance and market information, crucial for micro-enterprise success. Mahmood et al. (2014) highlight that marketing practices in women-led micro-enterprises often rely heavily on social networks, word-of-mouth, and community engagement, all forms of social capital. These studies collectively underscore the critical role of social capital in empowering women through micro-enterprises, particularly by enhancing their marketing practices and business outcomes.

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical framework for understanding women's empowerment through micro-enterprises and marketing practices integrates the Theory of Social Capital and the Resource-Based View (RBV) Theory. Social Capital Theory emphasizes the crucial role of social networks in providing women entrepreneurs with access to vital resources such as information, mentorship, and funding opportunities (Al Mamun & Fazal, 2018).

These networks facilitate the sharing of experiences and strategies, mitigating isolation often faced by women entrepreneurs, particularly in rural settings (Bennet & Richardson, 2005; Hoq et al., 2017). Complementing this, the RBV Theory highlights the importance of effectively managing and deploying critical resources like financial capital, human capital, and organizational capabilities to create value and achieve competitive advantage (Masakure et al., 2009). This framework posits that women's empowerment through micro-enterprises is achieved by leveraging social capital to access and enhance critical resources, while simultaneously applying RBV principles to optimize these resources. The synergy between these theories explains how women entrepreneurs can overcome challenges, innovate, and adapt to market conditions by investing in skills development, establishing robust financial management practices, and utilizing their unique social networks for marketing and business growth (Al Mamun & Fazal, 2018; Menzies et al., 2003; Robert D & Putnam, 2001).

Conceptual Model

The theoretical framework for the study posits a relationship between three key variables: marketing activities in micro-enterprises (independent variable), social capital (mediating variable), and women's empowerment (dependent variable). This framework suggests that marketing activities undertaken by women in their micro-enterprises, such as product development, pricing strategies, promotion techniques, and distribution methods, serve as the primary driver in the empowerment process. These activities contribute to the development and enhancement of social capital, which encompasses networks, relationships, and opportunities gained through marketing efforts.

Social capital, in turn, mediates the relationship between marketing activities and women's empowerment, measured across economic, social, familial, and political dimensions. The model proposes that as women engage more actively in marketing their micro-enterprises, they build social capital, which then translates into greater autonomy and decision-making power across various aspects of their lives. This framework underscores the critical role of marketing activities in initiating a chain of empowerment, highlighting how they can be leveraged as a strategic tool for driving women's empowerment in the context of micro-enterprises.

METHODOLOGY

The study employed a quantitative approach to examine the relationship between marketing activities in micro-enterprises, social capital, and women's empowerment. Data was collected through a survey conducted among 460 women members of micro-enterprises operating under the Kudumbashree Mission in Kerala, India, selected using multistage random sampling. Participants were required to have engaged in enterprise activities for at least three years, ensuring sustained involvement and likely achievement of a stable business state. The research instrument, a self-administered semi-structured questionnaire, was developed following a systematic literature review and adapted from previously validated scales to fit the study context. Marketing activities (independent variable) were measured through indicators such as product development, pricing strategies, promotion techniques, and distribution methods. Social capital (mediating variable) was assessed through measures of networks, relationships, and opportunities gained through marketing efforts. Women's empowerment (dependent variable) was quantified using four indicators: economic, social, familial, and political empowerment factors.

All constructs were measured using a five-point Likert scale and validated through exploratory factor analysis (EFA) and confirmatory factor analysis (CFA). The normality, communalities, linearity, reliability, and validity of the constructs were established before analysis. To examine the relationships among these variables, hypotheses were framed and tested. Data for all indicators were collected at a single point in time. Statistical techniques were applied using IBM SPSS 24.0 and AMOS 24.0 software packages. Path analysis was performed to estimate the significance of the hypothesized relationships between marketing activities, social capital, and women's empowerment. This methodology allowed for a comprehensive examination of how marketing activities in micro-enterprises influence women's empowerment through the mediating effect of social capital, providing robust empirical evidence to support the theoretical framework.

This path analysis primarily focuses on addressing the three major hypotheses listed below:

Hypothesis 1: Participation in marketing activities within micro-enterprises positively influences women's empowerment outcomes.

Hypothesis 2: Social capital moderates the relationship between marketing participation and empowerment outcomes for women in micro-enterprises.

The structural equation modelling technique was employed to test the two hypotheses pertaining the relationship between marketing activities, social capital, and attributes of women empowerment.

ANALYSIS, RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In this study, SPSS software was used for analysis, employing descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation, skewness, and kurtosis) and Cronbach's Alpha for reliability testing (Bayissa et al., 2017). Additionally, factor analysis incorporated KMO measures

and Bartlett’s test to assess variable relationships, and SEM analysis was performed to examine interactions between observed and latent variables.

Socio-Demographic Background of the Respondents

Table 1: outlines the sociodemographic characteristics of the women micro-entrepreneurs who took part in the survey

<i>Factors</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>%</i>	
Age	Up to 35	35	8
	36-40	131	28
	41-45	108	23
	46-50	58	13
	51-55	54	12
	56 & above	74	16
Marital status	Married	409	89
	Unmarried	10	2
	Others	41	9
Location	Rural	415	90
	Urban	45	10
Educational Qualification	Below SSLC	127	28
	SSLC	162	35
	HSE/ PDC	110	24
	Graduation & above	61	13
Total Monthly Household Income (Rs.)	Up to 20,000	58	13
	20,001 - 25, 000	101	22
	25,001 - 30, 000	125	27
	30, 001 - 35,000	55	12
	35,001 - 40,000	68	15
	Above 40,000	53	12
Duration of association of respondents with micro-enterprises	3- 4 Yrs	66	14
	4 -6 Yrs	201	44
	6-8 Yrs	53	12
	8-10 Yrs	101	22
	More than 10 Yrs	39	8

Source: Primary Data

Table 1 presents the socio-demographic background of respondents, highlighting key factors such as age, marital status, location, educational qualification, household income, and duration of association with micro-enterprises. The table shows that 28% of respondents (28%) are aged 36-40, with most being married (89%) and residing in rural areas (90%). Educational levels are distributed, with a third (35%) having completed SSLC and 28% with below-SSLC qualifications. In terms of income, 27% of households earn between Rs. 25,001 and Rs. 30,000 per month. A significant portion of respondents (44%) have been associated with micro-enterprises for 4-6 years, suggesting a stable, long-term engagement in their ventures.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha, a reliability test conducted using SPSS, measures the internal consistency of a measuring instrument. The results, based on a sample of 460, showed a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.873, suggesting strong internal consistency across the 43 items.

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.873	43

Factor analysis was deemed appropriate, supported by a Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure of 0.750 and a significant result from Bartlett's Test of Sphericity, indicating that the sample size and data were suitable for this analysis. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) revealed three core factors, accounting for 60.80% of the variance, with substantial variable loadings on each component. The component matrix indicated strong correlations, demonstrating the coherence of these factors and providing insight into the structure underlying the data set.

The Estimated Path Model

The path diagram for the preliminary model which is used for confirmatory factor analysis was as follows:

This path model represents the relationships between three main constructs: Marketing Activities (MA), Social Capital (SC), and Women's Empowerment (WE). The model shows

that MA, represented by indicators MA1 to MA10, has a positive influence on WE with a path coefficient of approximately 0.45. SC, represented by SC1 to SC7, also contributes positively to WE, with a path coefficient around 0.35. Furthermore, WE is measured by multiple dimensions, including Emotional Empowerment (EE), Social Empowerment (SE), Financial Empowerment (FE), and Personal Empowerment (PE), each with associated indicators (e.g., EE1-EE7, SE1-SE7). The path coefficients for these indicators range from 0.65 to 0.90, suggesting strong loadings on the WE construct, indicating that each sub-dimension significantly contributes to the overall empowerment construct. Indices for checking the fitness of the model:

	Model fit
Chi – Square	1598.543
Degrees of Freedom	857
CMIN/DF	1.124
CFI	0.732
RMSEA	0.034
NFI	0.916

The model fit indices provide insights into how well the proposed path model aligns with the observed data. A Chi-Square value of 1598.543 with 857 degrees of freedom suggests some deviation from a perfect fit, but this statistic is sensitive to sample size and often appears significant in larger samples. The CMIN/DF ratio (Chi-Square divided by degrees of freedom) is 1.124, which is within the commonly accepted threshold of less than 3, indicating a reasonably good fit. The Comparative Fit Index (CFI) of 0.732, however, is below the conventional cutoff of 0.90, suggesting room for improvement in model fit. On the other hand, the Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA) is 0.034, which is below the acceptable upper limit of 0.06, indicating a good fit for the population data. The Normed Fit Index (NFI) of 0.916 surpasses the typical threshold of 0.90, showing that the model has a relatively strong fit compared to a null model. In summary, while some indices suggest a need for potential model refinement (e.g., CFI), the low RMSEA and acceptable CMIN/DF and NFI indicate an overall satisfactory model fit.

Mediating Effect Model

Effects of Independent variable on Dependent Variable without the effect of Mediation variable.

Effects of Independent variable on Dependent Variable with the effect of Mediation variable.

Relationship		Direct Effect without Mediator	Effect with Mediator	Effect
Performance	Level of Participation	.190	.009	Full Mediation
Performance	Women Empowerment Factors	.042	.000	Partial Mediation

* Significant at 5% level

Standardized Total Effects (Group number 1 - Default model)

LP to SC = .199 SC to WE = .042

	LP	SC
SC	.222	.000
WE	.199	.042

Direct Effect without Mediator

LP to SC = .190 SC to WE = .042

	LP	SC
SC	.222	.000
WE	.190	.042

Effect with Mediator

Standardized Indirect Effects (Group number 1 - Default model)

LP to WE = .009 SC to WE = .000

	LP	SC
SC	.000	.000
WE	.009	.000

Marketing activities likely have a direct effect on women empowerment, which is expected to be strengthened or explained through the mediating role of social capital. In this model, marketing activities could directly improve women empowerment through enhanced

visibility, resources, or opportunities. However, social capital—represented by networks, relationships, and trust—may mediate this effect, suggesting that the influence of marketing activities on empowerment is partially or fully explained by how these activities enhance social capital. As the model indicates, increased social capital can boost empowerment by providing women with greater access to resources, collective action, and support systems, ultimately facilitating better outcomes in empowerment initiatives. If the direct path from marketing activities to women empowerment remains significant alongside the mediated path, this would indicate partial mediation, whereas if the direct effect diminishes significantly with the mediator, it would suggest full mediation.

DISCUSSION

The findings of this study provide compelling evidence for the positive influence of marketing activities in micro-enterprises on women's empowerment, mediated by social capital. The path analysis reveals a significant relationship between marketing activities and women's empowerment (hypothesis 1), with a path coefficient of approximately 0.45. This supports the theoretical framework positing that engagement in marketing activities serves as a primary driver in the empowerment process. The results align with previous research highlighting the transformative potential of micro-enterprises for women's socio-economic status (Mayoux, 2001; Kabeer, 2005). Furthermore, the mediating role of social capital (hypothesis 2) is substantiated by the model, demonstrating how marketing activities contribute to the development of networks, relationships, and opportunities that, in turn, enhance various dimensions of empowerment. This finding resonates with social capital theory, which emphasizes the importance of social networks in facilitating access to resources and opportunities (Coleman, 1988; Putnam, 2000).

The multi-dimensional nature of women's empowerment, as captured by the model's indicators of emotional, social, financial, and personal empowerment, underscores the comprehensive impact of micro-enterprise engagement. The strong factor loadings (ranging from 0.65 to 0.90) for these empowerment dimensions suggest that marketing activities and social capital contribute to a holistic empowerment experience. This multifaceted approach to empowerment aligns with Kabeer's (1999) conceptualization of empowerment as a process of change in multiple life domains. The study's focus on the Kudumbashree Mission in Kerala provides a contextual understanding of how grassroots initiatives can leverage micro-enterprises as a tool for women's empowerment. The significant mediating effect of social capital highlights the importance of collective action and community networks in translating economic activities into broader empowerment outcomes. This finding supports the arguments of scholars like Sanyal (2009) on the role of social ties in empowerment processes.

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that marketing activities in micro-enterprises are a significant mechanism for empowering women, with social capital acting as a vital mediator in this relationship. The findings suggest that marketing enhances women's visibility and access to markets and facilitates the formation of networks that enable women to access

resources and collective support, leading to greater empowerment. This dual pathway—direct marketing influence and the mediated effect through social capital—offers a comprehensive understanding of how enterprise activities can transform women's lives across multiple dimensions. The study also underscores the importance of focusing on social capital development in entrepreneurship programs aimed at women, as it significantly enhances the impact of business activities on empowerment outcomes. Despite the strengths of the study, such as the use of robust statistical methods (SEM and factor analysis), it has certain limitations. First, the cross-sectional nature of the data limits the ability to draw causal inferences about the relationships among variables. Longitudinal studies could provide a deeper understanding of how these relationships evolve over time. Additionally, the study is geographically limited to women micro-entrepreneurs in Kerala, India, which may limit the generalizability of the findings to other regions or cultural contexts.

Future research could address these limitations by employing longitudinal designs and expanding the scope to include diverse geographic and cultural settings. It would also be beneficial to explore the role of digital marketing in this framework, especially given the increasing importance of technology in business operations. Furthermore, future studies could examine other potential mediators or moderators, such as financial literacy or access to credit, which may also influence the relationship between marketing activities and empowerment. Understanding how different forms of social capital—bonding, bridging, and linking—affect women's empowerment in various contexts would also provide valuable insights. Overall, this study contributes to the growing body of literature on women's empowerment in entrepreneurship and offers practical implications for policymakers and development programs seeking to leverage marketing activities and social capital to improve empowerment outcomes for women in micro-enterprises.

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